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DIRECTIONS FOR DEVELOPING INVESTMENT ATTRACTION INTO UZBEKISTAN'S ECONOMY

Kurbonov Sanjar Sobir Ugli

Abstract: *This article is dedicated to studying the directions for developing investment attraction in Uzbekistan's economy, as well as analyzing the significance of investments in economic growth and the reforms being implemented in this area. Additionally, based on foreign experience, proposals and recommendations for improving the investment climate are presented. The approaches outlined in the article are of great importance for strengthening our country's economy and attracting international investments. The article proposes strategic approaches for more effective organization of the investment process.*

Keywords: *investments, economic reforms, investment climate, foreign experience, economic growth, investment strategies, international financial cooperation, investment promotion, economic efficiency, risk management, innovative technologies, global investment trends.*

Investments are one of the main factors in the development of the national economy, which allow accelerating economic growth, introducing new technologies and modernizing infrastructure. Today, in the context of global economic changes and the post-pandemic period, countries are seeking to attract foreign and domestic investments to make their economies more stable. In particular, the Republic of Uzbekistan has been paying special attention to improving the investment climate and infrastructure in recent years.

As part of the economic reforms being implemented in the country, important steps are being taken to create favorable conditions for investors and protect their legal interests. For example, within the framework of the "Uzbekistan - 2030" strategy, large-scale measures are being taken to encourage investment and attract domestic and foreign capital. In particular, efforts have been intensified to provide tax breaks, establish free economic zones, and eliminate administrative barriers.

At the same time, international experience shows that attracting investment has a positive impact not only on economic development, but also on regional and global integration processes. Based on the experience of developed countries, transparency, a stable political environment and the introduction of technological innovations are important in the formation of an investment strategy. Considering that the investment process is one of the factors necessary to ensure not only economic benefits, but also long-term social development, these aspects are also covered in detail throughout the article. Thus, this study serves as one of the important steps towards improving the investment climate at the national and international levels.

There are various scientific and practical sources on attracting investments to the Uzbek economy, which provide important guidelines for improving the investment climate in our country and increasing its attractiveness to international investors. For example, the World Bank's "Recommendations for a National FDI Strategy and Roadmap for Uzbekistan" report indicates the

need for the country to develop new strategies for attracting foreign direct investment (FDI). The report analyzes sectors with potential for economic growth and provides specific recommendations for improving the investment climate. These are important steps towards increasing Uzbekistan's economic stability and developing competitive sectors.¹

Also, in her article “Increasing investment attractiveness in the development of the national economy,” Vasila Usmonova, studying regional investment potential, emphasizes that regions such as Tashkent, Fergana, and Navoi are the most attractive for foreign investors, but regions such as Jizzakh, Surkhandarya, and Karakalpakstan need state support and infrastructure improvement. It is indicated that in order to increase investment potential in these regions, it is necessary to strengthen investment policy, ensure legal stability, and develop infrastructure.²

In addition, Ubaydulla Nadirkhanov's article “Foreign invested enterprises in the Republic of Uzbekistan: management tools, main forms, evolution and trends” analyzes the increase in the number of enterprises established on the basis of fully foreign capital and the positive impact this has on the country's investment climate. The article notes the need to improve the state's investment policy, noting that since 2020, the number of enterprises with fully foreign capital has exceeded joint ventures, which has increased investor confidence.³

This literature is the main source for analyzing the efforts being made to improve the investment climate in Uzbekistan and attract foreign capital. These sources serve to develop the necessary strategies to strengthen the country's economic growth and position in the international arena.

Investments in fixed capital play an important role in the economic development of Uzbekistan, as they create the necessary conditions for the growth of the country's industrial, infrastructure and other sectors. Attracting investments in fixed capital is important for ensuring the stability of economic growth, creating new jobs and implementing modernization processes in various sectors. Table 1 below shows the directions for developing investment attraction in the economy of Uzbekistan.

Table 1 Directions for developing investment attraction in the economy of Uzbekistan⁴

Directions	Description	Potential Impact
Legal reforms and regulation	Simplify the investment environment and legal system, strengthen guarantees for investors.	It increases investor confidence and makes it easier to attract investments.
Infrastructure modernization	Development and modernization of transport, energy, and communication infrastructure.	It increases the efficiency of production and trade activities, opens up new markets.
Development of innovation	Development of innovative	Creation and introduction of

¹<https://documents.worldbank.org/en/publication/documentsreports/documentdetail/099430406302241587/p17672901802190a108e00089316ad3dc7e>

²[https://api.scienceweb.uz/storage/publication_files/4708/20500/65c4671c3af2e__21_131_138_Advanced_FARINA__INCREASING+INVESTMENT+ATTRACTIVENESS+IN+THE+DEVELOPMENT+OF+THE+NATIONAL+ECONOMY%20\(1\).pdf](https://api.scienceweb.uz/storage/publication_files/4708/20500/65c4671c3af2e__21_131_138_Advanced_FARINA__INCREASING+INVESTMENT+ATTRACTIVENESS+IN+THE+DEVELOPMENT+OF+THE+NATIONAL+ECONOMY%20(1).pdf)

³ Nadirkhanov, U. (2024). Foreign invested enterprises in the Republic of Uzbekistan: management tools, main forms, evolution and trends. *European Journal of Economics, Finance and Business Development*, 71-79

⁴ Compiled by the author based on information

and high technologies	startups, technology incubators, and advanced research institutes.	new technologies, increasing economic competitiveness.
Attracting foreign investment	Expanding cooperation with international financial institutions and private investors	Attracting international capital and strengthening the country's integration into the global economic system.

At the same time, the state's economic policy, in particular measures aimed at improving the investment climate, has led to significant changes in the growth rate of investments in recent years. At the same time, global economic conditions, unexpected events such as a pandemic, can have a negative impact on investment processes. From 2010 to 2023, the Republic of Uzbekistan, like other countries, experienced various economic situations. We can see the picture of investment growth during this period in Figure 1 below.

Figure 1. Growth rate of fixed capital investments in the Republic of Uzbekistan⁵

The growth rate of fixed capital investments in the Republic of Uzbekistan is one of the important indicators for assessing economic development and the investment climate. An analysis of the period from 2010 to 2023 based on Figure 1 helps to better understand the impact of the country's economic policy, global economic conditions, and domestic reforms. The growth rate of investments during this period included stable, rapid growth, crisis, and recovery processes.

From 2010 to 2016, the growth rate of fixed capital investments in Uzbekistan was relatively stable, ranging from 100% to 111%. During this period, the country's economy continued to develop steadily, and this growth was attributed mainly to the state's economic reforms and efficient allocation of resources. Although fixed capital investments during this period were small, they ensured sustainable development in the economy. State investments in Uzbekistan's economic sectors, in particular agriculture and infrastructure, maintained a stable growth rate.

Since 2017, the growth rate of investments in Uzbekistan has increased significantly. It reached 119.4% in 2017, 129.9% in 2018, and 138.1% in 2019. During this period, significant changes have

⁵ <https://stat.uz/uz/rasmiy-statistika/investments>

occurred in the state's economic policy. President Shavkat Mirziyoyev's economic reforms, measures aimed at attracting foreign investment and improving the investment climate have been effective. In 2017, economic liberalization and modernization of the banking and financial system began in Uzbekistan. New legislation and incentives for foreign investors have been introduced, which has led to significant growth in these sectors. In particular, the growth rate of 138.1% in 2019 indicates the country's economic recovery and rapid adaptation to changing conditions.

2020 was undoubtedly a period of crisis for the global economy. Investment growth in Uzbekistan fell to 95.6%, reflecting the negative impact of the pandemic on economic activity. The COVID-19 pandemic, the suspension of international trade networks, the slowdown of production processes and the imposition of restrictions have led to a decline in the country's investments. The decline in foreign investments, as well as the suspension of domestic economic activity, significantly reduced investment growth in 2020.

After the pandemic, the process of economic recovery began in Uzbekistan in 2021–2023. Growth rates of 102.9% were recorded in 2021, 100.2% in 2022 and 123.4% in 2023. These indicators indicate that Uzbekistan has managed to restore economic activity after the pandemic and the investment climate in the country has recovered. In particular, the growth rate in 2023 reached 123.4%, providing confidence in the recovery and promising development of the Uzbek economy. This recovery is seen primarily as a result of new investment programs and economic policies implemented by the state.

In conclusion, the growth rate of fixed capital investments in the Republic of Uzbekistan changed in response to various economic conditions, reforms, and global challenges from 2010 to 2023. The stable growth in 2010–2016, rapid economic development in 2017–2019, the impact of the pandemic in 2020, and the recovery processes in 2021–2023 are a reflection of the important measures taken by the country to achieve economic growth and global conditions. This graph shows that Uzbekistan has achieved sustainable growth and development through proper management of economic reforms, global crises, and recovery periods.

In conclusion, attracting investments to the economy of Uzbekistan has achieved significant success in recent years. The implemented reforms and measures to improve the investment climate have served to strengthen the country's position in the international investment arena. The increase in the flow of foreign and domestic investments has created new opportunities in various sectors of the economy, ensuring long-term economic growth and stability.

The analysis shows that the most important factors in attracting investments are the development of the country's infrastructure, ensuring legal stability and creating favorable conditions for foreign investors. In particular, the measures developed within the framework of the "Uzbekistan - 2030" strategy serve as an effective basis for increasing the country's investment potential. At the same time, based on international experience, taking into account that cross-sectoral diversification and attracting investments aimed at a green economy are one of the important areas of economic reforms, the following proposals can be made:

1. Development of investment infrastructure. To effectively attract investments, it is necessary to modernize the transport, logistics, information technology and energy infrastructure. At the same time, it is necessary to create a favorable business environment for foreign investors through the development of free economic zones.

2. Continue legal reforms. It is necessary to ensure a transparent and stable legal environment that guarantees the protection of the rights and interests of investors. In particular, it is necessary to expand the legislative framework in line with international standards and reduce administrative barriers.
3. Ensure territorial equality. To attract investments not only in large cities, but also in regions with relatively low economic potential, it is necessary to introduce state incentive mechanisms. Tax breaks and special financial programs can be developed for these regions.
4. Invest in the green economy. In order to ensure environmental sustainability, special attention should be paid to attracting investments in green economy projects. This will not only help eliminate environmental problems, but also attract international financial assistance.
5. Expand international cooperation. Investment flows can be increased by developing economic cooperation with foreign countries. This includes strengthening close ties with international financial institutions and donor organizations.

By implementing the above measures, it is possible to achieve a new stage in attracting investment to the Uzbek economy and increase the country's competitiveness in the global economic system. This will serve long-term economic stability and prosperity.

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